

Poznań Living Lab

Creating a Climate-resilient City by Greening Educational Spaces

About this brief

This brief presents the Poznań case study, highlighting the environmental and social benefits generated through the Green Schoolyards initiative. The project is a multi-annual investment carried out in stages within the framework of EU territorial programmes, with four schoolyards greened in 2025.

The initiative strengthens urban resilience by:

- ▶ improving local microclimates and reducing heat stress for children in nine schools,
- ▶ increasing rainwater retention and mitigating flash-flood risks,
- ▶ enhancing biodiversity in compact urban areas, and
- ▶ providing students with accessible, nature-rich recreational spaces.

Context

Poznań, the capital of the Wielkopolska region in west-central Poland, lies on the Warta River near its confluence with the Cybina. Home to around 540,000 residents, it is the country's fifth-largest city and one of its oldest, with a rich architectural and cultural heritage dating back to the 10th century.

In recent years, Poznań has faced increasingly hot summers, rising average temperatures, and more frequent heatwaves, which particularly affect vulnerable groups such as children and pupils. Extensive soil sealing and dense real-estate development further limit urban ventilation and cooling, intensifying urban heat island effects. At the same time, progressive droughts have reduced surface water levels and groundwater retention. Although heavy rain now occurs more often, it runs off impermeable surfaces instead of replenishing groundwater, contributing to flash floods and infrastructure damage.

To address these climate pressures, the city is investing in multiple small-scale Nature-based Solutions (NbS) that strengthen green and blue infrastructure in compact urban spaces. The focus is on measures that enhance water retention, improve air quality, support biodiversity, and provide accessible green areas.

Within this effort, Poznań is leading a project to transform public schoolyards into greener, climate-resilient spaces, supported by funding applications to EU Integrated Territorial Investment programmes. The initiative covers nine schools and aims to improve microclimates, increase biodiversity, retain rainwater, and create natural recreational environments for school children aged 7-14. Investments to green all nine school yards are planned to be completed in 2028.

Digital version: Dziubala et al. (2026) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19660793>

Improving the quality of schoolyards

Examples of natural elements implemented in educational spaces in Poznań © City of Poznań; Photo: H. Bugajny

Transforming Schoolyards with NbS

The Green Schoolyards project converts paved, overheated schoolyards into functional green spaces using Nature-based Solutions (NbS). School designs must adapt to two realities: large outdoor areas that often include sports fields, and the diverse needs of school children aged 7-14. This requires solutions that support both active play and quieter recreational or educational activities.

4.05 hectares of newly built or upgraded public green infrastructure in urban areas to adapt to climate change, impacting **279 946 of estimated population**.

Designing Climate-Resilient School Grounds

Within the EU competition “Support for small water retention and green-blue infrastructure in the Poznań Metropolis,” the municipality develops projects that introduce unsealing of paved surfaces, diverse greenery, natural play and learning elements, and NbS that enhance biodiversity and retain rainwater.

Landscape architects replace artificial materials with natural, permeable surfaces and prioritise native plant species to improve shade, cooling, and habitat quality. These spaces also support outdoor education, offering children and teachers daily contact with nature that improves physical and mental well-being.

Did You Know?

Poznań’s ecological layout is shaped by **“green wedges”** formed by natural features, historic development, and river valleys. These corridors run north-south and east-west, linking the city to surrounding forests.

In the dense city center, the wedges narrow and fragment, making their protection crucial. Preserving these green areas – both centrally and on the outskirts – helps **improve air quality, absorb CO₂, reduce the urban heat-island effect, and manage water** more efficiently.

In dense urban areas, revitalised schoolyards function as small “play biotopes”, complementing existing and planned sports infrastructure.

Instead of traditional playground equipment, designs emphasise natural seating, small wooden elements, and “living nature laboratories” for biology, geography, and environmental learning.

This shift is especially important in Poznań, where many schoolyards built in the 1970s-1980s consisted largely of asphalt with minimal greenery.

Multi-Stage Implementation and Funding Path

Poznań finalised design documentation for four primary schools included in the first edition of Integrated Territorial Investments (ZIT). The funding application was submitted in 2024, with results and the start of construction scheduled for the first half of 2025. Another five schools have been selected for the following 2025 and 2026 editions.

Project design for primary school No. 82. Natural elements, unsealing surfaces © City of Poznań

The project's financing story reflects its evolution:

Initial stage: participatory design funded by the city; planned implementation using Norwegian funds failed, and projects were not realised.

Current stage: the City of Poznań continues to finance design work, while EU funding, especially through ZIT, provides a breakthrough enabling actual implementation. Stable long-term financing remains a challenge.

Planned stage: the goal is to establish a permanent city-funded programme covering design, construction, and environmental education, ensuring continuity and strategic impact.

Inclusive Planning and Community Engagement

The project aims to redesign and revitalise schoolyards into spaces that support both the school community and the wider urban ecosystem. New designs introduce NbS such as expanded greenery, natural recreational areas, permeable surfaces, and rain gardens that cool, absorb water, and improve biodiversity.

All participating public schools enter the programme through a structured co-creation phase. This typically begins with workshops involving teachers, school children, parents, administrators, and landscape architects. These sessions help identify local needs, expectations, and on-site challenges, ensuring that the final concepts respond to real community priorities.

Co-Design Principles and Capacity Building

The co-creation process is guided by principles of transparency, shared goals, flexibility, experimentation, reflection, and inclusiveness. Engaging all stakeholder groups strengthens ownership of the designs and builds practical skills within the school communities. This collaborative approach now serves as a transferable model for other urban projects in Poznań.

Workshop with school community allowed us to gather valuable insights, understand the needs of the community, and identify potential challenges and opportunities within the school grounds © City of Poznań

Benefits of NbS in Schoolyards

Social Benefits (long term benefits)

- ▶ Supports school children's physical health and mental well-being.
- ▶ Stimulates creativity and cognitive development.
- ▶ Enhances the sensory and visual quality of school environments.
- ▶ Provides accessible green areas for local communities beyond school hours.
- ▶ Encourages innovation in NbS design and environmental education.
- ▶ Ensures inclusivity through accessible paths, quiet zones - everyone will find space for themselves.

Ecological Benefits

- ▶ Increased biodiversity and ecosystem resilience.
- ▶ Reduced urban heat island effect through shading and cooling.
- ▶ Improved rainwater infiltration and groundwater replenishment.
- ▶ Creation of micro-habitats for insects and beneficial soil organisms.

Economic Benefits

- ▶ Use of recycled or biodegradable materials lowers construction and waste-related costs.
- ▶ Reduces infrastructure damage.
- ▶ Improves storm water management and reduces long-term drainage system costs.

Cost Overview

Implementation & Maintenance Costs

Implementation covers technical preparation (site assessments, hydrological studies, and design documentation), skilled labor (landscape architects, engineers, specialized contractors), materials (permeable surfaces, native plants, rainwater systems, natural furniture), and construction works such as unsealing surfaces, planting, and installing infrastructure.

The total average cost per school is **686,000 EUR**. Maintenance costs for green areas amount to **23,000 EUR** per school over a 5-year period following project completion.

Additional material

- ▶ Lienhart, L., Kernitzky, M., Weiß, V., Türk, A., Taddeo, S., Dziubala, A., Bronikowska, M., Chen, W., Mourits-Andersen, S., Coelho, B., Telling, N.L., Holm, M. (2025). Report on demand and supply chains in NbS - Invest4Nature Deliverable 3.4. Horizon Europe Grant No. 101061083
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17511376>

The economics of nature-based solutions

Invest4Nature

Invest4Nature aims to attract investments in one of the key measures of climate change adaptation and risk reduction: **nature-based solutions**

In Invest4Nature's vision to create flourishing markets for nature-based solutions (NBS), it **aims** to:

- Create thorough understanding of **the economic costs and benefits** of NBS to enable the creation of business models and suitable market conditions for NBS
- Develop a **decision support** tool to enable private & public stakeholders make **informed decisions** on NBS investments
- Create a multi-stakeholder **online marketplace**
- Establish a European NbS **investment community**

5 Living Labs

Austria, Denmark, Norway, Poland and Portugal

with **NbS cases** covering five landscapes:

Partners

Coordinator

NBS Living Labs

Learn more:

Funded by the European Union

Invest4Nature

/communities/Invest4Nature

Explore more Invest4Nature Briefs

